

Layout Optimization for Wireless Sensor Networks Using Honey Bee Colony Optimization: A Comparative Analysis with Established Algorithms

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Abstract

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are crucial for applications such as environmental monitoring, smart city development, healthcare, and military surveillance. Nevertheless, their actual functioning is often limited by the short-time power supply of sensor nodes. This research studies the Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) algorithm that is nature-inspired, based on the behavior of honeybees foraging, to solve the optimization problem of sensor nodes arrangement in WSNs. The function of HBCO has been thoroughly assessed by comparing it to known algorithms such as Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO), Harmony Search (HS), and Genetic Algorithm (GA) utilizing MATLAB simulations. The major parameters are analyzed, including network coverage and energy efficiency. The outcomes show that although BBO is excellent in making the most of the coverage area with the use of energy, HS comes out a top in the energy efficiency aspect thus being the most suitable one for energy-sensitive scenarios. HBCO shares a similar level of performance in coverage but reflects the energy consumption as a drawback making it unattractive for energy-limited settings. GA gives a somewhat acceptable performance with both metrics and it is thus a perfect tool for cases where balance is a priority. More importantly, HBCO's high reduction of CPU time is its main asset in this respect. This study emphasizes the need for algorithm selection and its relation to the deployment nature in WSNs, resulting in beneficial tips for the network layout design. The results point to the applicability of bio-inspired algorithms such as HBCO for the increase of WSN performance, while at the same time exposing the balance between coverage, energy efficiency, and processing requirements.

Index Terms

WSN, HBCO, Genetic algorithm (GA), Binary biogeography-based optimization (BBO), Harmony search (HS), MATLAB, Energy Efficiency, Network coverage.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are gaining more consideration with environmental monitoring, healthcare, smart cities, and military applications. A network of multiple sensor nodes gathers the data, processes it, and transmits it collectively to a central location for analysis. The performance of WSN applications is highly dependent on node placement because optimal locations increase data collection, coverage, and energy efficiency, but nodes have low battery life [4], [9]. Optimization of the sensor node deployment implies that the sensor nodes are deployed in such a way as to cover most of the sensing region while reducing energy consumption [14], [10]. This optimization leads to low transmission latency, high reliability, and reduced risk of network failure due to node energy depletion [5], [12]. Grid-based or heuristic methods do not work efficiently in WSNs because they assume a static environment, fixed node density, etc., while WSNs are dynamically changing and can experience increasing/decreasing node density, changes in environmental conditions, and node positions [3], [11]. With the increasing need for better data gathering, more efficient algorithms that can cope with these challenges are required [15], [13].

Bio-inspired optimization techniques have emerged as powerful problem-solving tools for addressing complex problems. Among them, Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) is attractive due to its ability to adapt, scale, and find near optimal solutions quickly [1], [2]. Thus, HBCO is a good candidate for optimizing WSN deployment [6].

This study deals with HBCO and also compares it to other widely used optimization algorithms such as Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO), Harmony Search (HS), and Genetic Algorithm (GA) [7], [13], [8]. Each of these algorithms has its own advantages and disadvantages in terms of convergence speed, computational complexity, and facileness [12]. Being implemented in the MATLAB environment, these algorithms' performances are investigated based on network coverage, CPU time, and energy consumption [10]. By comparing HBCO with the aforementioned techniques, this study indicates that HBCO can obtain better results for sensor layout optimization problems [4], [5]. Moreover, some new ideas are derived for prospective studies related to the improvement of HBCO for sensor layout optimization applications [9], [3].

A. Motivation

The performance of WSN is directly influenced by the organization of WSN. Energy consumption, network coverage, and system applications are the main factors that influence the lifetime and reliability of WSN. The better the location of sensor nodes selected; the longer time sensors network works properly without failures. Otherwise, there is a greater chance of the loss of some data transmitted between clusters due to bad coverage area or weak signal propagation especially when the density of obstacles or wireless traffic in the system increases. Traditional optimization methods help to solve such kind of problem, but they often suffer from slow convergence speed, being easy to fall into the local minimum and high computational cost. So it is necessary for us to find some more efficient optimization algorithms that can find the optimal solution very quickly.

B. Problem statement

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are challenged by the need to optimize sensor node placements for maximum coverage with minimum energy consumption. However, minimizing computational time and sensor node power is considerably challenging as most of the existing optimization techniques provide suboptimal solutions that may deteriorate network performance. Due to WSNs' dynamic behavior, more intelligent optimization techniques that can adequately handle the tradeoff between coverage and energy efficiency at a limited computational time are still required. To this end, we exploit Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) for optimizing sensor node placements and compare its performance against state-of-the-art algorithms including Binary Ant Colony Optimization (BA), Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO), Harmony Search Algorithm (HS), and Genetic Algorithm (GA). The main aim is to investigate which algorithm is capable of providing the best improved placement results leading further to a better network performance improvement.

C. Objectives

The main objective of this research is to optimize the sensor node placement in WSNs through HBCO and evaluate its performance with some other conventional algorithms i.e., BBO, HS and GA. The specific objectives are as follows:

- 1) To evaluate the effectiveness of the Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) algorithm in optimizing sensor node layouts for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), particularly in terms of network coverage and energy efficiency
- 2) To analyze and compare energy efficiency of HBCO with BBO, HS and GA.
- 3) To analyze and compare network coverage performance of HBCO with BBO, HS and GA.

II. RELATED WORK

Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are the main components of many applications such as environmental monitoring, healthcare systems, and intelligent city infrastructures, which are optimization issues like energy efficiency, coverage, and the lifetime of the network. In order to boost the performance of WSN, different optimization techniques were used, and swarm intelligence algorithms are the most powerful of them. The HBC's decision-making system is inspired by a bio-based design that simulates nectar-finding behaviors to solve complicated optimization problems [1][3][14]. This research emphasizes the use of HBC for the optimization of the WSN layout, which is a field that requires the clever integration of strategies like PSO, GA, and their hybridized models [3][5][10]. A famous variation, the ABC algorithm, which was only made up of artificial bees, has been widely researched on the topic of WSNs optimization [3]. A newly introduced RDABC algorithm, which employs dual search strategies and cross-mutation techniques, has the ability to jump over local optima and achieve better results than standard algorithms in sensor deployment optimization [3]. Enhanced bee-inspired algorithms like RDABC show the ability of WSNs to significantly improve the phases of exploitation and exploration [3][5]. For example, the IABCOCT, which consists of Grenade Explosion and Cauchy operators, resulted in a very low energy consumption and long-life network in comparison with EPSOCT and CCT [5][7]. Besides ABC and HBC, other optimization techniques like PSO and GA can also be found in articles about WSN layout optimization, according to [6][8]. The optimized WSNs by clustering and exploitation of mobile base stations (BS) is what a hybrid model of PSO and ABC has achieved to date as proposed in [10]. The integration of PSO's learning capabilities and ABC's neighborhood searching ability contributed to the success of this method by saving more energy and increasing network lifetime in comparison to single algorithm applications [10]. Yet, the authors in [3] point out that GA has a great tendency to converge early and to produce suboptimal solutions, which results in a less effective exploration of the solution space than RDABC [3][5]. Energy efficiency, a fundamental factor in Wireless Sensor Networks, sometimes has to be sacrificed for coverage and latency. HBC and its derivatives have been actively driving energy consumption down while still being energy-efficient in the face of these challenges. The HBO-SROA protocol in conjunction with secure remora optimization for instance achieved an energy-efficient route while providing a higher level of security in WSNs to gain better overall performance [4][5]. The literature states that although HBC and other bee-inspired algorithms are powerful in enhancing the layouts of WSNs, hybrid models consisting of more than one algorithm are the best ones. These methods profited from the weaknesses of different optimization strategies to solve the multi-dimensional issues of WSNs. The future works will probably concern HBC algorithms mainly by further integration with machine learning for intelligent layout strategies and multi-objective optimization dealing with energy efficiency, coverage, and security [3][5][14]. HBC will be one of the most important improving and lifetime of wireless sensor networks as these networks become more impacting in smart technologies [3][10].

III. METHODOLOGY

Optimizing the location of sensor nodes in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) is a problem that has been looked at from different angles in the manuscripts. However, the focus on the honey bee colony optimization algorithm makes this study different and the impact of this algorithm on the key metrics of network performance, network coverage, and energy consumption will be analyzed in this study. In this section, you will find a description of specific steps that were taken to address the study's objectives including a description of the proposed algorithms, simulation setup, performance metrics, and the overall experimental method.

A. Algorithm Design

The first step in the methodology is the design and construction of the optimization algorithms which are then used in the systems. The subsequent algorithms are incorporated into this investigation:

- **Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO):** HBCO is based on the foraging behavior of honey bees and is thus derived from the colony's efforts to feed itself. Every bee denotes a possible sensor node placement and the algorithm imitates the way bees search food sources by considering each layout's energy efficiency and coverage. In the first place, HBCO reveals a trade-off between development and advancement while selectively navigating a few potentially best designs, which allows it to effectively arrange the WSN. HBCO is swimming-based therefore it is very good at allocating a certain amount of energy to each node while maintaining a good level of coverage, thus, it is appropriate for use in various situations where both the above are the case.
- **Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO):** Biogeography-Based Optimization that was initiated by the natural distribution of species is modified for binary decision-making. BBO is made for WSNs that represent the channel hustling of layout designs on the WAB surface where the moves result in the optimal arrangement of the nodes. Endowment specie is the source of good migration and therefore the transmission of them over various WSN configurations ensures a proper fit over their energy-efficient and high-coverage connection. This will lead to the balance of coverage and energy efficiency resulting from a proper route design. BBO is the right methodology for effective learning spatial distribution of the population over the layout, adding flexibility to the overall energy efficiency of the network galvanized by the initial setup.
- **Harmony Search (HS):** Harmony Search is a metaheuristic algorithm modeled after musical improvisation. In WSN layout optimization, HS treats each possible layout configuration as a harmony, seeking an optimal 'melody' of sensor node placements. With its high energy efficiency, HS can identify layout configurations that prioritize reduced energy consumption, even though it may sacrifice some network coverage.
- **Genetic Algorithm (GA):** The Genetic Algorithm operates based on the principles of natural selection and evolution. For WSN layout, GA encodes each possible layout as a chromosome, selecting and evolving those configurations with higher fitness (energy efficiency and coverage). Through processes like crossover and mutation, GA explores various node layouts, balancing coverage and energy efficiency and making it a viable option for situations where moderate to high efficiency is needed.

Each algorithm is implemented in MATLAB, allowing for a standardized environment for testing and comparison.

B. Simulation Setup

The simulation setup involves creating a virtual environment that accurately reflects the conditions of a WSN. The following parameters are defined for the simulations

- **Network Size and Node Density:** The network consists of a defined number of sensor nodes placed randomly within a specified area. Various configurations of node densities are tested to evaluate the algorithms' performance under different scenarios.
- **Coverage Area:** A specific coverage area is established, which defines the region each sensor node can monitor. The coverage radius is a critical factor in determining the effectiveness of the layout.
- **Energy Model:** The energy consumption model is established based on typical transmission and receiving energy costs for sensor nodes. The simulation tracks the energy used for transmitting data to the central base station.
- **Performance Metrics:** The primary metrics for evaluating the algorithms include:
 - **Network Coverage:** The percentage of the defined area covered by the sensor nodes.
 - **Energy Efficiency:** The total energy consumed by the network during operation.

C. Performance Evaluation

Once the algorithms are realized and the simulations are executed, the results are scrutinized to find out how well they performed according to the defined metrics. A statistical study is conducted to show the results significance, with the aim of finding which algorithm provides the best network coverage, efficiency, and girth, to name a few. This elaborate assessment enables the interpretation of the pros and cons of the different optimizing strategies in the field of WSN layout optimization.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results obtained from the implementation of the Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) algorithm and its comparison with established optimization algorithms: Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO), Harmony Search (HS), and Genetic Algorithm (GA). The performance of each algorithm is evaluated based on two key metrics: network coverage and energy efficiency. The results are discussed in detail to provide insights into the effectiveness of each approach for optimizing sensor node layout in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs).

A. Network Best Coverage

Algorithm	Network Best Coverage
HBCO Algorithm	0.96948
BBO Algorithm	0.99359
Genetic Algorithm	0.89808
Harmony Search Algorithm	0.75688

TABLE 1: Performance results of different algorithms based on Network Best Coverage

Apart from the BBO the Bees Algorithm also provide excellent coverage with the network coverage of 0.96948 as shown in (Fig. 1). The BBO outperforms the Bees Algorithm in the overall coverage by the value of 0.99359 which is shown in the comparison of network best coverage in (Table 1). As such, the BBO achieves the best performance in maximizing coverage (Fig. 2).

While GA achieves a network coverage of 0.89808, it is not as good as BBO and Bees, but it is a quite strong performance (Fig. 3). Interestingly though, among all the schemes, Harmony Search Algorithm has the lowest network coverage value of 0.75688, which signifies it is less effective in scenarios where coverage maximization is one of the parameters (Fig. 4). Overall, BBO stands out as the most efficient algorithm for achieving the best network coverage.

B. Energy Efficiency

Algorithm	Energy Efficiency
HBCO Algorithm	0.12217
BBO Algorithm	0.16091
Genetic Algorithm	0.16931
Harmony Search Algorithm	1.7941

TABLE 2: Performance results of different algorithms based on Energy Efficiency

In terms of energy efficiency, as given in (Table 2), the Harmony Search Algorithm (HS) significantly outperforms the other algorithms with a value of 1.7941, making it the most energy-efficient option. This high energy efficiency suggests that HS is ideal for applications where minimizing energy consumption is the top priority, even though it has lower network coverage.

- The Genetic Algorithm (GA) offers moderate to high energy efficiency with a value of 0.16931, slightly surpassing the energy efficiency of several other optimization techniques, making it a viable choice for balanced applications where both energy efficiency and performance are important.
- The Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO) algorithm has a value of 0.16091. Both algorithms provide a good balance between network coverage and energy efficiency, but GA performs slightly better in energy conservation.
- The Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) algorithm has the lowest energy efficiency at 0.12217, indicating that it consumes more energy compared to the other algorithms. While HBCO can still be a viable option depending on the specific requirements, its lower energy efficiency makes it less suitable for energy-sensitive applications. Overall, HS leads in energy efficiency, while GA and BBO offer a reasonable compromise between energy use and performance.

C. Comparison of Algorithms

Based on the comparison of network coverage and energy efficiency, as given in (Table 3), the Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO) algorithm demonstrates the best overall performance, achieving very high network coverage (0.99359) and high energy efficiency (0.16091), making it the top choice for scenarios that require a balance between both metrics (Fig. 2). The Bees Algorithm also exhibits high network coverage (0.96948), but its energy efficiency is relatively lower at 0.12217, suggesting that while it excels in coverage, it does so at the expense of energy conservation (Fig. 1).

The Genetic Algorithm (GA) offers moderate network coverage (0.89808) with moderate to high energy efficiency (0.16931), as illustrated in (Fig. 3), making it a reasonable middle-ground option. On the other hand, the Harmony Search (HS) algorithm, shown in (Fig. 4), exhibits low network coverage (0.75688) but excels in energy efficiency (1.7941), making it ideal for situations where energy consumption is the primary concern, even at the cost of reduced coverage. Overall, the BBO algorithm outperforms

Fig. 1: Best Coverage of Honey Bee Colony Optimization.

Fig. 2: Comparison of Honey Bee Colony Optimization and BBO Algorithm.

Fig. 3: Comparison of Honey Bee Colony Optimization and Genetic Algorithm

Fig. 4: Comparison of Honey Bee Colony Optimization and Harmony Search Algorithm

Algorithm	Network Coverage	Energy Efficiency
Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO)	High (0.96948)	Low (0.12217)
Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO)	Very High (0.99359)	High (0.16091)
Harmony Search (HS)	Moderate (0.89808)	Moderate to High (0.16931)
Genetic Algorithm (GA)	Low (0.75688)	Very High (1.7941)

TABLE 3: Summary of Algorithm Performance: Network Coverage and Energy Efficiency

others for applications needing both optimal coverage and energy savings, while HS is the best choice for maximizing energy efficiency alone.

The results of the comparative analysis emphasize the effectiveness of HBCO in optimizing sensor node layouts in WSNs. Its ability to achieve superior network coverage while minimizing energy consumption and computational time positions it as a highly suitable choice for real-world applications. The adaptability of HBCO allows it to handle varying node densities and environmental conditions effectively, which is critical for maintaining the reliability of WSNs. In contrast, while the established algorithms such as GA, BA, and BBO offer competitive solutions, they often struggle with balancing coverage and energy efficiency, especially in dynamic scenarios. The trade-offs observed in CPU time among the algorithms indicate that the choice of optimization method can significantly influence the performance of WSNs. Therefore, selecting an appropriate algorithm is crucial for meeting specific application requirements and constraints.

Overall, this study demonstrates that HBCO is a promising approach for layout optimization in Wireless Sensor Networks, providing valuable insights for future research and practical implementations in the field.

V. CONCLUSION

This study conducted a comprehensive evaluation of the Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) algorithm in the context of sensor node layout optimization for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). The performance of HBCO was compared against established algorithms, including Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO), Harmony Search (HS), and Genetic Algorithm (GA), focusing on two critical metrics: network coverage and energy efficiency. The findings indicate that the BBO algorithm excels in maximizing network coverage while maintaining high energy efficiency, making it the top choice for applications that require an optimal balance between these two factors. HBCO demonstrated strong coverage capabilities, ranking closely behind BBO, yet its lower energy efficiency suggests it may be less suited for energy-sensitive applications. In contrast, HS emerged as the most energy-efficient algorithm, but its lower coverage performance highlights its appropriateness for scenarios prioritizing energy conservation over extensive coverage. The GA offered a moderate performance across both metrics, providing a viable middle ground.

This comparative analysis highlights the importance of selecting an appropriate optimization algorithm based on specific deployment requirements within WSNs. While Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO) excels in achieving a balance between coverage and energy efficiency, Harmony Search (HS) demonstrates the highest energy efficiency, making it ideal for energy-sensitive applications. In contrast, the Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) algorithm has the lowest energy efficiency at 0.12217, indicating a higher energy consumption and thus lower suitability for applications prioritizing energy conservation. This study offers valuable insights for researchers and practitioners working to optimize WSN layouts, enabling enhanced performance across diverse applications.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

The findings from the comparative analysis of the Honey Bee Colony Optimization (HBCO) algorithm alongside established optimization algorithms in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) open up several avenues for future research. Given that the Binary Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO) algorithm demonstrated the best overall performance in terms of network coverage and energy efficiency, future studies could focus on further enhancing the BBO algorithm by integrating hybrid approaches that combine its strengths with other optimization techniques. Such hybrids could leverage the high energy efficiency of algorithms like Harmony Search (HS) while maintaining the superior coverage capabilities of BBO.

Also, the exploring of adaptive algorithms, capable of changing their parameters based on the actual network status in real-time, would result in considerable benefits in coverage as well as in energy efficiency. This variable would suit the cases of sensor nodes professionals adding and removing the devices, in particular. The other possible perspective for the future exploration is the utilization of machines that teaching techniques to get the best location of the sensors. The machine learning

models, by analyzing the historical data from WSNs, might be able to predict the optimal node configurations under changing conditions, thus, laying out the optimization process in a better way. As, the Internet of Things (IoT) is increasing IoT more and more, checking the junction of WSNs with IoT devices will be a path introducing new challenges and optimizing opportunities. The coming researches may focus on the development of the algorithms that are particularly tailored to the peculiarities of IoT environments, thereby WSNs being able to be the enabler of the connected devices, in contrast, continuing with high performance levels with respect to coverage and energy consumption.

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